

Practical and Extension Activities for Teaching of Electric Power Quality Concepts

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ABSTRACT The importance of power electronics (PE) in society is indisputable, providing comfort and productivity with energy efficiency and the use of alternative power sources. However, with the benefits of PE, there are also challenges in maintaining the quality of electrical energy, affected by the intermittency of renewable sources, the presence of harmonic distortions, fluctuations, and voltage imbalances, among other adverse effects. Therefore, teaching concepts about power quality is essential for the training of future electrical engineers, allowing them then to identify and assess problems that could interfere with the correct functioning of electroelectronic equipment. In this sense, the purpose of this work is to share the actions that have been undertaken in the electrical engineering course to complement the teaching on power quality in such a way that they can be used by other educational institutions. Extension activities involving industries and companies in the region are presented, in which power quality data are collected for later analysis and feedback for students. In addition, a didactic workbench is proposed to carry out experimental activities, where the student can install and observe through a power analyzer the influence of different types of load on voltage and current waveforms and on quality indicators. In this way, students are provided with comprehensive and applied training in this area, with the aim of connecting theoretical knowledge to real-world situations.

KEYWORDS Didactic workbench, extension activities, power quality, teaching.

I. INTRODUCTION

Power electronics (PE) is an essential area in modern society, allowing the development and application of technologies that benefit us daily. Whether it is in the generation and distribution of electricity, in the automotive industry or in residential electronic equipment, PE plays a crucial role, providing energy efficiency and environmental sustainability. On the other hand, PE has direct impacts on power quality (PQ), generating voltage and current disturbances that can affect the proper operation of the equipment [1]. Therefore, teaching about power quality should be part of the curriculum of electrical engineering courses, presenting concepts and regulations that can contribute to identifying problems.

Teaching about power quality initially consists of the theoretical presentation of the phenomena involved, such as steady-state voltage variation, the occurrence of voltage fluctuations or imbalances, the existence of harmonic distortions, among others. However, the assessment of power quality depends on the availability of data on voltages and currents in the installation or electrical network under analysis, which implies the use of dedicated equipment for this purpose.

Therefore, the verification of the power quality implicitly depends on a practical activity, related to the installation and configuration of the PQ meters, as well as the subsequent extraction and analysis of the collected data. This analysis must be based on the indicators and limits proposed in the

regulations and technical guidelines [2], [3], helping evaluate the quality of the electrical energy.

Normally, commercial or industrial consumers are only concerned with the quality of service provided by distributors, related to the availability of electricity in their facilities. Even so, when economic losses start to occur due to improper operation or equipment damage, the interest in PQ becomes relevant and electrical parameters are monitored.

In this sense, the purpose of this work is to share practical experiences carried out in the Electrical Engineering course, aimed at improving teaching on power quality. For this, a prepared laboratory environment will be described so that students can perform measurements safely, observing the influence of different types of load on the PQ indicators. Additionally, reports are presented on extension activities that involve the analysis of PQ in local industries and businesses, highlighted the importance of this type of action for student training and external agents to teaching institutions.

II. THEORETICAL ACTIVITIES

In the Electrotechnics Department at the Federal Institute of Santa Catarina (IFSC), theoretical knowledge about power quality is taught to students during in-person classes in the Electrical Engineering undergraduate course and Master's degrees in Electrical Energy Systems. In these courses, the

subjects of Power Quality and Efficiency (60 h) and Power Quality (30 h) are offered respectively.

In theoretical classes, information is provided about the causes and consequences of the main power quality phenomena, involving steady-state voltage, current and voltage unbalance, current and voltage harmonics, short-term dips, overvoltage and interruptions, flicker, power factor and frequency variation. For these parameters, the indicators, procedures and limits provided in PRODIST-8 [2] and IEEE 519 [3] are used. In addition, criteria for carrying out measurements, specifications of some commercial PQ meters and types and limitations of current probes are presented.

This knowledge is reiterated through an academic assessment, in which students receive data from measurements of electrical parameters in commercial and industrial facilities and are requested to analyze whether the power quality on site is satisfactory or not. In this case, the work performed is part of the extension activity proposed in Section IV, in which after the students find a nonconformity with respect to technical recommendations, they must determine causes and possible solutions to the PQ problem.

III. PRACTICAL ACTIVITIES

To exercise practical activities on power quality, a teaching workbench is organized. The block diagram is illustrated in Figure 1. The workbench consists of a 7.5 kVA three-phase system, which is powered by a delta-star transformer with a 380 V line voltage on both the primary and secondary sides. A line impedance of 3.52% is added to the phase and neutral

FIGURE 1. Didactic workbench block diagram. Different types of linear and nonlinear loads are used to change power quality parameters on the point of common coupling (PCC).

conductors on the secondary side, with the aim of emulating the cable length impedance of a conventional distribution network. The transformer and line impedance specifications are highlighted in Table 1.

Figure 2 demonstrates the implemented workbench. The proposed use of the didactic workbench is to perform power quality measurements at the point of common connection (PCC), considering the presence of different types of load. The resistive load consists of three residential heaters (1.0 kVA), connected to each phase of the network. Capacitive and inductive load are implemented using a three-phase reactor (1.0 kVA) and bank capacitor (1.2 kVA) with star and delta connection, respectively. The intention is to simulate an inductive displacement factor condition and compensate with capacitive reactive power. Furthermore, it is verified that there is a resonance caused by the interaction between the capacitor bank and the secondary side inductance.

TABLE 1. Transformer and line impedance specifications.

Parameter	Value
Transformer power	7.5 kVA
Primary coil voltage (V_1)	380 V
Transformation ratio (N_T)	1.7545
Primary resistance (R_1)	1.235 Ω
Primary reactance (X_1)	0.798 Ω
Secondary resistance* (R_2)	0.907 Ω
Secondary reactance* (X_2)	0.798 Ω
Core-loss resistance* (R_c)	3042 Ω
Magnetizing reactance* (X_m)	1174 Ω
Primary side base impedance ($Z_{1,b}$)	57.8 Ω
Transformer impedance ($Z_{T,pu}$)	4.83 %
Conductor Resistance (phases and neutral) (R_L)	650 $m\Omega$
Conductor Reactance (phases and neutral) (X_L)	196 $m\Omega$
Secondary side base impedance ($Z_{2,b}$)	19.3 Ω
Conductor Line impedance ($Z_{L,pu}$)	3.52 %

*Parameters referenced to the primary side.

FIGURE 2. Image of teaching workbench. A computer is used to visualize in real time the electrical parameters measured by the PQ analyzer.

A. Rectifiers

Passive rectifiers with a capacitive output filter are used as the main generators of current harmonic components. One three-phase rectifier and three single-phase rectifiers are implemented with the prototype illustrated in Figure 3 and with the specifications of Table 2. Each rectifier has switches to allow the inclusion of 1 mH inductors, which represent an input impedance of approximately 2% per phase. Similarly, the total output capacitance (400 μ F) can be changed, by switching two groups of capacitors (165 and 235 μ F). Thus, it is possible to modify the physical parameters of the rectifiers and demonstrate their influence on PQ.

B. Passive Filter

To demonstrate the possibility of reducing harmonic distortion, a passive filter is implemented to attenuate the third-order harmonic current component. It is considered a shunt-type filtering structure, with an inductor and a capacitor (in series) connected between phase and neutral conductors.

The passive filter implemented is exemplified in Figure 4. Inductors and capacitors of 18 mH and 45.5 μ F are used, respectively, providing a 176 Hz tuning frequency. This value is slightly below the third harmonic frequency (180 Hz), anticipating a possible loss of filter tuning caused by the aging of the capacitors [4], [5]. Due to the resistance of the components, the filter quality factor is around 30.

TABLE 2. Rectifier specification.

Parameter	Value
Rectifier bridge model	SDK 25/12 (Semikron)
Input AC inductance	1 mH
Maximum output capacitance	400 μ F
Heatsink thermal resistance	6.3 $^{\circ}$ C/W
Single-phase resistive load	194 Ω
Single-phase power	0.7 kVA
Single-phase power factor	0.66
Three-phase resistive load	145 Ω
Three-phase power	2.1 kVA
Three-phase power factor	0.86

FIGURE 3. Diode rectifier prototype. Four PCBs are used, of which three are connected as a single-phase and one as a three-phase rectifier.

C. Induction motor and air conditioners

Three-phase induction motors are common in industrial electrical installations. As a result, a set of motor drive is connected to the teaching bench, as seen in Figure 2. This set has a 1.5 hp (1.8 kVA) induction motor connected to a magnetic brake. The machine is activated directly or through an inverter (WEG CFW500). As the inverter model does not have any type of input filter, the impact of this equipment on the current harmonic components can be identified.

Similarly, the laboratory infrastructure has two air conditioning units, which can be connected to the bench. This equipment is installed in separate rooms of 15 m² each, one of which is a traditional air conditioner with on/off control (Gree Eco Garden) while the other is an inverter air conditioner (Samsung Wind Free). Both equipment are 12,000 BTU and have a high energy efficiency rating (Class A according to Inmetro/Brazil classification). It is known that equipment with an inverter has a superior energy efficiency than a traditional air conditioner. However, because of the presence of a single-phase rectifier, the inverter conditioner contributes to the increase of current harmonics in the power supply network and to the degradation of PQ indicators.

D. Didactic Proposal

To carry out practical and extension activities on power quality, the laboratory has two PQ meters, as illustrated in Figure 5(a). The Yokogawa CW-500 model is used for measurements in industrial facilities, having current probes for 1,000 A. For didactic workbench activities, the IMS P-600 model is used. This equipment has 200 A current probes, which allow measurements with an adequate accuracy of 2 A. Furthermore, through the manufacturer's software and the connection of the equipment to a computer via USB cable, it is possible to view waveforms and power quality indicators in real time. The PQ meter is connected to the PCC, as exemplified in Figure 5(b).

In practical activities, the teaching proposal initially consists of presenting personal protection items and electrical safety procedures. As shown in Figure 5 (c), the students are equipped with clothing, a helmet, and protective glasses.

FIGURE 4. Passive filter for attenuating the third order harmonic current.

FIGURE 5. Use of the didactic workbench: (a) PQ meters available in the laboratory; (b) Connection of the PQ meter to the PCC; (c) Students connecting equipment and using personal protective items.

Considering that the power panel is energized, the student who connects the measuring equipment receives a pair of gloves for electrical contact. Students are instructed to connect the probes in locations that provide mechanical stability, preventing accidental disconnections from occurring during the measurement period. Furthermore, attention is drawn to the precision required to avoid phase switching between voltage and current probes, and to observing the direction of the current to prevent measurement errors.

E. Measurements and Analysis

After the PQ meter is connected, the power quality parameters are observed in the computer. Different load conditions (LC) are selected through the load control panel, according to Table 3. Electrical parameters measured for each operating condition are presented in Table 4.

Initially, steady-state voltage without load is perceived in Figure 6 (LC=01). The workbench supply voltage is verified to have a THD of 2.6%. This value is similar under resistive or resistive-inductive load conditions (LC=02 or 03). Due to the presence of inductive reactive energy, the current lags behind the voltage (cf. Figure 6, LC=03), reducing the power factor (PF) to 0.94. The power factor is restored by inserting the capacitor bank, as seen in Figure 6 (LC=04). However, despite the displacement angle between voltage

TABLE 3. Didactic workbench load conditions (LC).

LC	Description
01	No load (open circuit)
02	Resistor
03	Resistor + Reactor
04	Resistor + Reactor + Capacitor
05	Rectifier (1 ϕ)
06	Rectifier (3 ϕ)
07	Rectifier (1 ϕ) + Rectifier (3 ϕ)
08	Rectifier (1 ϕ) + Resistor + Reactor + Capacitor
09	Rectifier (1 ϕ) + Resistor + Reactor + Harmonic filter
10	Induction motor
11	Induction motor + Capacitor
12	Induction motor + Inverter
13	Induction motor + Inverter + Capacitor
14	Air conditioner (on/off)
15	Air conditioner (inverter)

and current being practically eliminated, oscillations are observed in the current waveform. This effect is caused by the series resonance between the capacitor bank and the circuit inductance (transformer and conductors), resulting in a resonance frequency around 755.6 Hz (close to the 13th harmonic) [6]. Therefore, even with a low amplitude voltage harmonic component in the power supply, the low impedance created at the resonance point provides noticeable changes in the current waveform.

The effect of non-linear loads on power quality is demonstrated in load conditions 05, 06 and 07. The waveforms provided by the single-phase rectifier are exemplified in Figure 6 (LC=05). According to Table 4, the single-phase rectifier provides a THD_i greater than 100%, mainly due to the presence of the harmonic current component of order 3. Because the third harmonic has the same phase angle in the three-phase conductors, the linear sum of these components occurs in the neutral conductor. This contributes to the neutral current (I_n) being greater than the phase currents (I_{abc}), according to Table 4 (5.3 A and 4.0 A respectively). Furthermore, THD_v increases from 2.5% (LC=01) to 5.0%, highlighting the negative impact on PQ.

Similarly, Figure 6 (LC=06) shows the waveforms with the activation of the three-phase rectifier. Due to the presence of current harmonics, the THD_v increases from 2.5% (LC=01) to 5.1%. Since the amplitude of the supply voltage phases are not exactly equal, an asymmetry occurs between the supply current pulses, as seen in Figure 6 (LC=06). Combining the loads of single and three-phase rectifiers, the waveforms in Figure 6 (LC=06) are obtained. In this load condition, THD_v increases from 2.5% (LC=01) to 6.1%.

To explore the use of passive filters and reduce the harmonic content of the current, it's suggested a combined load condition, with waveforms demonstrated in Figure 7 (LC=08). In this situation, $THD_v=5.1%$, $THD_i=35.3%$ and the capacitor bank is used only to counterbalance the reactive

FIGURE 6. Voltage and current waveforms at the PCC for load condition (LC) from 01 to 07, described in the Table 3.

power of the inductive load. Furthermore, although the loads are balanced, there is a neutral current of 4.9 A, derived from the third harmonic current generated by the single-phase rectifiers. The neutral current (i_n) is illustrated in Figure 7 (LC=08).

FIGURE 7. Phase voltage (v_b), phase current (i_b) and neutral current (i_n) waveforms in the PCC, at load conditions (LC) 08 and 09 (with capacitor bank or third harmonic passive filter respectively).

TABLE 4. Measurement results for each load condition.

LC	V_{abc} [V]	I_{abc} [A]	I_n [A]	S_{abc} [kVA]	PF	THD_v [%]	THD_i [%]
01	227.2	-	-	-	-	2.6	-
02	220.4	4.4	-	0.96	1.00	2.6	2.6
03	219.1	4.6	-	1.02	0.94 _i	2.6	2.6
04	221.0	4.6	-	0.98	0.99 _c	3.3	9.1
05	224.9	4.0	5.3	0.69	0.96 _i	5.0	106.2
06	223.8	3.2	-	0.72	0.86 _c	5.1	52.5
07	220.5	5.4	5.7	1.20	0.90 _i	6.1	41.9
08	219.2	6.8	4.9	1.49	0.93 _c	5.1	35.3
09	220.3	7.3	2.6	1.61	0.89 _c	3.3	24.7
10	222.4	2.5	-	0.56	0.77 _i	2.6	3.8
11	222.4	1.9	-	0.43	0.99 _c	2.8	15.7
12	223.9	2.6	-	0.58	0.77 _i	5.2	77.1
13	225.5	3.1	-	0.69	0.63 _c	6.2	78.5
14	223.0	4.3	4.3	0.92	0.99 _c	2.6	11.8
15	223.0	3.3	3.3	0.72	0.90 _i	2.8	45.5

Subsequently, the capacitor bank is replaced by the passive third-harmonic filter, providing the waveforms in Figure 7 (LC=09). In this situation, the neutral current is reduced to 2.6 A, and THD_v , THD_i become 3.3% and 24.7%, respectively. Although some power quality parameters have improved (related to the harmonic content of voltage and current in the PCC), it is observed that the power factor reduces from 0.93 to 0.89. This occurs because the capacitors chosen for the passive filter provide a capacitive reactive power greater than what the electrical installation requires. Therefore, it is important to size the capacitive portion of the passive filters, to adequately compensate for the existence of the inductive reactive in the electrical installation.

The waveforms provided by connecting the three-phase induction motor are shown in Figure 8. Initially, at LC=10

(without inverter), the delay of the current waveform in relation to the supply voltage is verified, providing an inductive power factor of 0.77 and a THD_i of 3.8%. Inductive reactive power is compensated for by including the capacitor bank at $LC=11$, improving PF to 0.99. Even so, in the same way as presented for $LC=04$, the inclusion of the capacitor bank causes a resonance frequency close to the 13th harmonic, generating the oscillations in the current waveform seen in Figure 8 ($LC=11$). Thus, the THD_i increases to 15.7%.

In the workbench, the induction motor can also be powered via a voltage source inverter. As shown in Figure 8 ($LC=12$), the motor and inverter assembly requests a distorted current waveform from the electrical network, similar to Figure 6 ($LC = 06$). The inverter internally has a three-phase diode rectifier to perform the AC/DC conversion, providing values of $PF=0.77$, $THD_v=5.2\%$ and $THD_i=77.1\%$.

Typically, the problem of low PF is solved by inserting a capacitor bank. This alternative is beneficial, as observed in situations $LC=04$ and $LC=11$, with the presence of only inductive reactive power. However, when low PF is caused by the presence of non-linear loads (and distortion reactive power), the insertion of a capacitor bank worsens the problem, as seen in Figure 8 ($LC=13$). Then, the PQ parameters degraded to $PF=0.63$, $THD_v=6.2\%$ and $THD_i=78.5\%$.

The influence of air conditioning equipment on energy quality is demonstrated under load conditions 14 and 15. Figure 9 ($LC=14$) illustrates the waveforms of a traditional air conditioner, which internally has a compressor with a single phase induction motor and operates with a hysteresis control method (on/off). For this load, the measured PQ parameters are $PF=0.99$, $THD_v=2.6\%$ and $THD_i=11.8\%$. High PF indicates that there are capacitors internally to compensate for the reactive power of the compressor.

In contrast, Figure 9 ($LC=15$) presents waveforms from an inverted-type air conditioner. A single phase diode rectifier is used to power the DC/AC stage, taking into account the similarity of the waveform i_b according to that seen in Figure 6 ($LC=05$). Even so, it appears that the equipment manufacturer is concerned about PQ, employing technology to reduce current harmonic distortion. The measured PQ parameters are $PF=0.90$, $THD_v=2.8\%$ and $THD_i=45.5\%$, highlighting that the inverter type, although more efficient, causes a greater degradation of the PQ parameters than traditional air conditioning.

IV. EXTENSION ACTIVITIES

Extension activities are carried out in industries and local companies, with the intention of obtaining real data for teaching purposes while contributing to the safety and productivity of these partners. There is a great demand for these extension activities, sought out either by companies facing problems in operating their equipment or by those curious to know the quality of energy at the connection point.

Today, according to Resolution n° 7/MEC/CNE/CES [7], extension activities must comprise at least 10% of the total

curricular workload of undergraduate courses. Therefore, taking measurements and producing reports on power quality

FIGURE 8. Voltage (v_b) and current (i_b) waveforms in the PCC, due to the connection of the three-phase induction motor at load conditions (LC) from 10 to 13 (with and without inverter and capacitor bank).

FIGURE 9. Voltage ($v_{a,b}$) and current ($i_{a,b}$) waveforms, due to the connection of on/off ($LC=13$) or inverter air conditioner ($LC=14$).

are opportunities for students to meet the additional requirements of the Electrical Engineering program.

In 2018, a pilot study on power quality was carried out at the IFSC medium voltage substation [8], [9]. The activity served as the basis for the definition of measurement procedures, which began to be applied to other electrical installations outside of the institution. At the moment, eight companies have already participated in extension activities, which usually involve more than one point of analysis. Table 5 presents some information on electrical installations (EI) in which PQ studies took place. The parameters presented correspond to the elements of the medium voltage substation of the electrical installation. In all cases, the input and output line voltage is 13.8 kV and 380 V respectively.

A. PQ meter connection

The extension activities begins with sending a letter of intent. This letter defines the responsibility of the company (access to installations and electrical diagrams) and the educational institution (measuring equipment, data analysis, presentation of results). If the terms of the agreement are accepted, the project's advisors perform a technical visit to recognize the electrical installation and identify the measuring point. If safe access to the measurement point is feasible, the PQ meter is installed, which remains in place for up to 15 days. In Figure 10 are some images of the PQ meter connection. After this period, the professors return to the site to disconnect the measuring equipment. Visits to the measurement site are always accompanied by an employee of the company. For safety reasons, no students are involved in the measurement stage. Later, they can return for another technical visit with a lower level of contact with risk locations.

B. Measurement analysis

The data collected are downloaded from the measuring equipment and provided to students in subjects of power quality. Students also receive information about electrical installation, which is necessary for the application of technical recommendations (as is the case with [3]). Transformer data, conductor gauge, the length up to the measurement point and capacitor bank values are provided according to Table 5.

The data collected are then analyzed by students based on the technical information taught during theoretical lessons. The indicators are extracted and verified in relation to the limits set out in [2], [3]. All power quality parameters mentioned in Section II are taken into account.

C. Results

After analyzing the data and interpreting the power quality parameters, the students must prepare a report with the results obtained. This report is delivered to the company involved and corresponds to the feedback material from the extension activity. Results of PQ measurements implemented during extension activities are demonstrated below.

1) Steady-state voltage

The steady-state voltage amplitude is checked using the procedure defined in [2]. The occurrences in the precarious (DRP) or critical (DRC) voltage range are calculated from samples collected every ten minutes. According to [2], DRP and DRC must be a maximum of 3% and 0.5% respectively. As shown in the Table 6, most of the electrical installations (EI) analyzed are in accordance with these values. However, the EI=1 displays a problem regarding this PQ parameter, with reports of permanent damage to electronic equipment.

In Figure 11 (a), the steady-state voltage remains in the precarious or critical range most of the time. This observation is confirmed by the graphs in Figures 11(b) and (c), in agreement with the DRP indicator. It can be concluded that half of the voltage samples in the precarious range occur during daytime hours (7 am to 6 pm), and correspond to the period of greatest energy consumption. Furthermore, these occurrences are distributed throughout the week, proving they are not influenced by business days or weekends.

Further investigation demonstrated that the transformers are configured to receive a voltage lower than 13.8 kV, with the aim of correcting it by selecting the appropriate transformer tap. However, the local power utility reported that the grid voltage at the site is 13.8 kV, which indicates that the customer's power substation is what's creating the power quality problem. In this case, it is necessary to conduct a corrective maintenance action to change the transformers tap to connect it to the medium voltage network.

FIGURE 10. Connection of PQ meters to companies' main energy panels.

TABLE 5. Medium voltage substation parameters (13.8 kV / 380 V) of the analyzed electrical installations (EI).

EI	Instal. Power [MVA]	Transf. Quant. [Qty]	Transf. Imped. [%]	Cond. Gauge [mm ²]	Cond. Phase [Qty]	Cond. Length [m]	I _L [A]	I _{SC} [kA]	Gen. Power [MVA]	Cap. Bank [kvar]	Type of activity (load)
1	1.50	3	7.30	300	2	15	443	10.4	–	50	Educational institution
2	1.50	2 ^a	5.45	120	4	10	980	21.7	–	322.8	Shopping mall (chiller)
3	0.50	1	5.37	185	1	15	295	13.7	0.5 ^b	42.5	Supermarket
4	0.30	1	5.78	185	2	120	350	5.4	0.5 ^b	10	Supermarket
5	2.10	3 ^a	5.72	185	3	20	600	18.9	1.8	120	Logistics distribution center
6	0.30	1	5.02	120	2	43	275	7.9	0.33 ^b	15	Optical lens industry
7	2.25	3 ^a	6.01	240	3	20	348	18.9	–	90	Electronic product industry
8	0.75	1	5.20	240	3	8	520	21.8	0.30	12.5	Office building

^a Transformers in parallel. PQ measurements and analyzes were performed on only one of the transformers.

^b The generator is activated from 6:30 to 9:30 pm.

TABLE 6. Power quality indicators for electrical installations (EI).

EI	DRP [%]	DRC [%]	UF _v [%]	ΔI [A]	UF _i [%]	PF	P _{st} [pu]
1	52.1	32.8	0.72	171.3	22.5	≥ 0.92	0.31
2	1.8	23.5	0.66	11.7	1.1	≥ 0.92	0.35
3	0.0	0.0	0.60	32.8	4.3	≥ 0.92	2.53
4	0.4	0.0	1.15	58.0	12.7	≥ 0.92	1.11
5	0.0	0.0	0.57	18.7	1.8	≥ 0.92	0.17
6	0.0	0.0	0.63	31.0	6.8	≥ 0.92	–
7	13.7	19.2	0.92	63.5	5.6	≥ 0.92	0.44
8	7.2	0.0	0.97	41.5	3.7	≥ 0.92	0.23

Elevated DRP and DRC indicators can also be noted at EI=2,7,8. In these locations the steady-state voltage above the appropriate level occurs at early morning time (0 am to 7 am) or on weekends. At these times, most of the equipment is turned off, which means that the voltage drop is reduced. Considering that the equipment is prepared for this high voltage condition, these EI do not have a PQ problem, despite the numerical indicators showing otherwise.

2) Voltage and current unbalance

The voltage unbalance factor (UF_v) is predicted in [2] and must be less than 3%. According to Table 6, no problems were identified in relation to this PQ parameter in the electrical installations analyzed. On the other hand, significant current unbalance is observed at EI=1. Although current unbalance is not considered in [2], this fact can cause overheating at certain points of the transformer, increased conduction losses and neutral voltage in relation to the ground [10], [11]. To quantify the unbalance, the largest current difference between the phases (ΔI) is determined, which represents 95% of the samples collected (95% percentile). Subsequently, the current unbalance factor (UF_i) is calculated considering ΔI and the nominal current of the transformer, as proposed in [8]. Thus, it appears that EI=1

FIGURE 11. Example of steady-state voltage recording (EI=1 of Table 6): (a) 3-phase samples; distribution of voltage transgressions for the precarious range by time group (b) or week days (c).

has a current imbalance greater than 22%. This situation requires the redistribution of single-phase loads between phases to avoid damage to the transformer over time.

3) Power factor and voltage fluctuation

No low power factor (PF) problems were identified. In the electrical installations analyzed, the predominant reactive power is due to the presence of electric motors. In this case,

the inductive reactive power is compensated with automatic capacitor banks, which act dynamically to maintain the PF above 0.92.

The voltage fluctuation was below 1 pu in most cases in regards to the parameter P_{st} and the procedure provided in [2]. However, at EI=3 and EI=4 the limit was exceeded. Although P_{st} and the remained below 1 pu most of the time, it was greater than 3pu in the period between 6:30 pm to 9:30 pm. In these cases, the source of the problem is the energy generator, which is connected during this period to reduce contracted demand costs. Although the issue was identified by the PQ meter, consultation with site workers did not indicate that any flickering in the lights was perceived. Possibly, as the lighting of the location is done with LED luminaires, the electronic ballast is capable of compensating for voltage fluctuations and keeping the lighting of the location below the visual sensitivity threshold.

4) Voltage and current harmonic distortion

The Table 7 shows the voltage harmonic distortion values measured in electrical installations. The distortion values are presented according to [2]. Indicators of even harmonic components ($HD_{v,p}$), odd non-multiples of three ($HD_{v,i}$), odd multiples of three ($HD_{v,3}$) and total harmonic distortion (THD_v) are calculated and compared to the limits of 2.5, 7.5, 6.5 and 10% respectively. In all measurements, only the $HD_{v,i}$ parameter of EI=7 had exceeded the limit.

The relevance of harmonic current components in electrical installations is analyzed based on IEEE 519 [3]. For all EI, the highest individual current harmonic distortion factor (HD_i) is due to 3rd- or 5th-order components, which contribute significantly to total demand distortion (TDD). From the TDD and HD_i values presented in Table 7, it is evident that EI=1, 6 and 7 exceed the recommended limit of harmonic current distortion. This conclusion considered the ISC/IL ratio of electrical installations and the limits set out in Table 2 of [3].

V. CONCLUSIONS

The activities presented in this work have improved the teaching about power quality at IFSC. It appears that students

show greater interest and curiosity in the technical content presented during lectures.

The practical activities exercised on the didactic workbench demonstrate many of the energy quality problems found in industrial installations. Furthermore, it allows students to take part in obtaining measurements in a more inclusive and safe way (contrary to what would be observed if they went directly to an energy substation, for example).

Extension activities not only collect realistic experimental data to be used for teaching but also generate valuable technical information for owners of electrical installations. This information can be useful in identifying (and avoiding) equipment degradation and problems in industrial production processes. In addition, extension activities bring the educational institution closer to the real world, providing students with the opportunity to learn by doing.

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AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTIONS

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PLAGIARISM POLICY

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TABLE 7. Voltage and current harmonic distortion indicators.

EI	$HD_{v,p}$ [%]	$HD_{v,i}$ [%]	$HD_{v,3}$ [%]	THD_v [%]	HD_i [%] ($3 \leq h < 11$)	TDD _i [%]
1	0.1	4.2	1.3	4.4	10.4 ^(3rd)	10.7
2	0.0	2.9	0.1	2.9	2.8 ^(5th)	3.2
3	0.1	3.9	0.9	4.0	5.8 ^(5th)	6.8
4	0.1	3.5	0.9	3.6	3.8 ^(5th)	4.2
5	0.3	3.1	0.4	3.2	4.9 ^(5th)	5.2
6	0.2	4.9	1.9	5.0	7.9 ^(5th)	10.8
7	0.1	7.8	1.0	7.9	18.6 ^(5th)	20.2
8	0.2	4.1	0.7	4.2	5.9 ^(3rd)	7.9

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